

EFFECT OF OIL SPILL ON ECOLOGY OF FORCADO RIVER IN DELTA STATE, NIGERIA.

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Key words:

*Oil Spillage,
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Normalize
burnout ratio*

Abstract: *The aim of the study as to assess the ecological risks of oil spill effect on Forcado River in Delta State, Nigeria; four objectives guided the study; identify the oil spillage locations between 2010 to 2020, analyse the effect of oil spill on the abiotic ecological factors, analyse the impact of oil spillage on the identified ecological factors, evaluate the fire incidence caused by oil spill to the environment using the Normalized Burn Ratio (NBR) from 2010 to 2020, to carry out this research, Geographic information system (GIS) and remote sensing (RS) tools were used to assess the effect of ecological risk of oil spill on Forcado River in Delta State, Nigeria. The Landsat satellite imagery of 2010, 2015 and 2020 with 30 meters resolution and the Advanced Space borne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER) were used for the study. The geospatial Database of the oil spill record was collected from National Oil Spill Detection and Response Agency (NOSDRA). The oil spill geospatial database in excel sheet format was imported to ArcGIS 10.1 to map out the oil spill spot in the study area. The principal component analysis (PCA) was applied to the indices to assess the major ecological factor affected in the study area. The zonal statistical Analysis was used to estimate the impact of spillage on the ecological factor. The Normalized Burn Ratio was used to highlight the burned areas and estimate severity of fire. The study found that from 2010 to 2020, the health of the vegetation and wetland in the Forcado River area significantly deteriorated due to oil spills. A total of 294,996.42 hectares of the ecological environment were affected, with the wetland being the most impacted (185,150.07 ha), followed by water bodies (69,810.48 ha), farmland (2,255.4 ha), and forests (light forest: 490.41 ha, thick forest: 12,205.62 ha). Sand dunes (4,923.99 ha) and shallow water areas (18,060.84 ha) were also contaminated. Therefore, it is very important to evaluate the regional ecological environment from the combined effects of multiple ecological factors Ecological Index (EI). The EI index should be recommended for assessment of*

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Ecological factor impacting in oil spill because is completely based on the index of remote sensing information and natural factors.

INTRODUCTION

Oil spillage is a global environmental issue that has been reoccurring since the discovery of petroleum oil and gas, which was part of the industrial revolution. The total spillage of petroleum oil and gas into the land, and water bodies through human activities is estimated to range from 0.7 to 1.7 million tons per year (Agu, 2015). In recent times, oil spills have posed a major threat to the environment of the oil producing areas, and if it is not effectively checked can lead to the total destruction of ecosystems and even extinction of some animal species especially fishes (Eze and Eseoghene, 2018).

Oil spills can occur on land, where their effects are relatively easier to manage. However, when they happen in marine environments, they often lead to oil pollution, causing significant environmental hazards, which result in serious ecological risks and long-term environmental disturbances (Chen, Zhang, Wan, Li, Huang, and Fei, 2019). The primary causes of oil spills in the sea are linked to the transportation of oil via tankers and pipelines (Challenger, Gmur, Taylor, 2021). The severity of damage from oil spills varies depending on the oil's chemical makeup, the affected area, and the cleanup methods used. The sensitivity of organisms to the pollution depends on their nature and life cycle (Eze and Eseoghene, 2018). Additionally, organisms not directly impacted by the spill may still experience indirect effects due to changes in community structure and interactions such as grazing,

predation, and competition dynamics (Chen et al., 2019).

Considering oil spills as a form of pollution, the United Nations Convention defines pollution as the direct or indirect introduction by humans of substances or energy into the environment, which can cause harm to living resources, marine life, human health, marine activities, water quality, and amenities (Omofonmwan and Odia, 2017). Based on these perspectives, oil spills are classified by their severity. Major oil spills cause extensive contamination to coastal shorelines, resulting in significant ecological damage to near-shore communities. Since oil was discovered in Nigeria in the 1950s, the country has faced ongoing environmental degradation from oil development. The expansion of Nigeria's oil industry, combined with rapid population growth and weak enforcement of environmental regulations, has caused extensive damage to the environment, particularly in the Niger Delta (Egwu, 2016).

Environmental risk assessments have traditionally been presented in non-spatial formats. However, this has changed significantly over the past decade. Advances in Remote Sensing and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) have greatly enhanced the spatial representation and analysis of various types of information and data. As a result of these technological developments, environmental risk mapping of pollutants has progressed rapidly (Lahr and Kooistra, 2010).

Statement of the Research Problems

The oil spills within the Niger Delta were one of the most important reasons to select the region as one of the most ten polluted places around the globe in Blacksmith Institute, (2013). The oil spill among other factors has induced internal displacements in the Niger Delta by aggravating the level of poverty in the area. Network of oil pipelines within the Niger Delta are under constant threat of rupture, sabotage, theft, vandalism and terrorism and these have resulted in oil spill, explosion and deaths. Sabotage and oil pipeline breakage sequel to damages and ruptures are some of the major causes of oil spill in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. Ruptures within the Niger Delta occurs sequel to diminished pipeline integrity and the aging process of the pipes. This has increased the amount of oil spillage into the environment which can cause severe damage to the environment and to surrounding vegetation when they leak into the soil thereby posing great threat.

In the light of these that, this work intended to assess the ecological risk of crude oil spill on Forcado River in Delta State Nigeria using multiple Optical Remote sensing technique. The research will assess the spatial and temporal patterns of oil spill distribution along the Forcado River and its surrounding areas. Remote sensing allows for the effective monitoring of large and difficult-to-access regions, providing a comprehensive view of the extent of contamination. This methodology also facilitates the tracking of oil spill movements over time, helping to identify areas of recurrent pollution

and the impact of environmental factors such as tides and flooding on the spread of oil.

Objectives of the study

The aim of this study was to carry out an ecological risk assessment of oil spill on forcado river environment in Delta State. The investigation was achieved through the following specific objectives.

1. To identify the oil spill locations from 2010 to 2020 in the study area.
2. To analyse the effect of oil spill on selected abiotic ecological factors such as temperature, wetland, land use and land cover during the study period.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Ecology

Ecology focuses on studying the relationships between organisms and their environments. The environment consists of two distinct components: abiotic (non-living or physical elements) and biotic (living or organic elements) (Balasubramanian, 2019). Despite their distinction, these two components are closely interdependent, and it can often be difficult to separate the biotic from the abiotic, especially when considering the environment's role in shaping human biology and culture (Ordinioha and Brisibe, 2013).

Ecology is a purely scientific field that seeks to understand how organisms interact with their broader environment. Like any science, the findings from ecological studies do not prescribe ethical or political actions. This distinction is important because the environmental movement has infused the term 'ecology' with political significance. While ecology can and should inform political decisions, students of ecology

must approach their research with scientific rigor (Saleh Mamman and Abdullahi, 2015).

Impact of spillage on the ecological factors

Oil spills significantly impact the ecosystems where they occur, particularly affecting vulnerable mangrove forests. It's estimated that 5 to 10% of Nigeria's mangrove ecosystems have been destroyed due to settlement and oil activities. The once-extensive rainforest, covering about 7,400 square kilometres, has also largely disappeared (ANEEJ, 2004). In populated regions, spills can spread widely, contaminating soil and groundwater, which damages crops and aquaculture. Bacteria consuming the spilled hydrocarbons deplete dissolved oxygen, leading to fish deaths. In agricultural communities, an entire year's food supply can be lost in an instant. The negligent practices of oil operations in the Delta are making the environment increasingly uninhabitable (ANEEJ, 2004). Wadsworth (Anejionu O., Ahiamunnah P., Nri-ezedi C., 2015) notes that oil spills can contaminate agricultural land and livestock, but preventive measures like relocating cages, transferring livestock, and early harvests can mitigate these effects. He emphasized the need for collaboration among ship owners, the government, and private entities to address the challenges posed by oil spills and explored management strategies for fisheries and aquaculture post-spill. According to Anejionu et al. (2015), oil spills can harm the environment in three main ways: through the poisoning of agricultural products, direct contact, and habitat destruction.

GIS tools have been utilized to study various oil spill incidents in the Niger Delta. For example, Nwankwoala and Nwaogu (2009) used ArcGIS 3.5 to identify water bodies in Etche Local Government as significant dispersal factors for oil spills. Their study demonstrated GIS's capability to monitor, and model affected areas and recommended creating Environmental Sensitive Index (ESI) maps for practical use. The integration of GIS tools enhances the understanding of the temporal and spatial distribution of oil spills. Ivanov and Zatyagalova (2008) combined remote sensing and synthetic aperture radar (SAR) data to map oil spills in the Gulf of Thailand, showing that such combinations improve spill identification and classification.

Effective management of oil spills depends on accurate data and information. Aukett (2012) suggested that overlaying GIS layers of spill data with environmental data and trajectory modeling outputs enhances management efforts by identifying at-risk and sensitive areas, guiding the development of targeted strategies. Aukett also highlighted the clarity and conciseness of GIS presentations in facilitating communication about spill management. This study employed a combination of GIS tools for overlay analysis to aid decision-making in managing and preventing the detrimental effects of future oil spills.

STUDY AREA

The Forcados River is a channel located in the Niger Delta of southern Nigeria, situated between 5°0'0" to 7°0'0" East and 5°0'0" to 6°30'0" North. It stretches approximately 198 kilometers (123 miles) and flows into the sea at the Bight of Benin in Delta State. This river is a

vital route for small ships. It branches off from the Niger River at the same location as the Nun River. Local communities have relied on fishing in this river for many years, transporting their catch to the Niger River for sale, storage, and personal use. In the early 20th century, Forcados served as a port for steamers from England until it became silted. The Forcados River is a key navigable channel in the Niger Delta, leaving the main Niger River about 20 miles (32 kilometers) downstream from Aboh. It flows through areas of freshwater and mangrove swamps, as well as

coastal sand ridges, before reaching the Bight of Benin. Since around 1900, it has been the primary route for small ship traffic between the Niger River and the Gulf of Guinea. The ports of Forcados and Burutu, located 15 and 20 miles (24 and 32 kilometers) upstream from the Bight, facilitate trade; however, much of the agricultural produce transported down the Niger and Forcados rivers is exported from Warri, a Delta port linked to the river by the 25-mile (40-kilometer) Warri River.

Figure 3.4: Hydrological Map of the Study Area
(Source: Extracted from Researcher’s GIS lab, 2022)

Research Design

The research design used in this study primarily involved a Satellite-Based survey. Quantitative data were gathered from historical records, allowing the study to measure the rate of oil spill expansion and assess its impact on the area. The design incorporated a combination of other

Projected population of the study area.

S/N	Community	Population (2016)	Population (2018)	Population (2020)
1	Iduwumi,	22,335	22,398	22,424
2	Kolorugbene,	22,456	22,520	22,545
3	Agbodobiri	24,375	24,444	24,472
4	Okrika	47,345	47,479	47,533
5	Egodor	21,010	21,070	21,093
6	Obatebe	23,367	23,433	23,460
7	Benibayo	22,345	22,408	22,434
8	Operemor	24,744	24,814	24,842
Total		207,977	208,566	208,803

Source: Authors' laboratory 2022

Data analysis

The data analysis involves the method used to achieved the objective the study. Data processing system typically manipulates raw data into information and likewise information system typically takes raw data as input to produce information as output.

Data Presentation and Analysis of Results Location of Oil Spill Within the Study Area.

The Map (Figure 5.1) shows the spatial distribution of oil spill in the study area between 2010 to 2020. The Samples used for analysis were collected in eleven locations with findings as follows: (I) There was a massive oil spill along

research methods, including historical analysis, case studies, and data presentation and analysis. This multi-method approach was employed because a single method did not provide sufficient results, so each method complemented one and the other.

Company A (SPDC), four (4) Inches Yokri pipeline at Well 114s flowline, which affected the Vegetation, Surface Water and Topsoil. The spill was within the company's right of way. (2) Another location of oil spill was along 6 inches Yokri pipeline Cluster and 51 Bulkline B2 - Manifold 4. the oil spill affected Vegetation and soil, the spill was within the company's right of way. (3) There was also SPDC 6" Yokri Manifold 1 Cluster 95 Bulkline at Obotobo it was noticed that a section of Bulkline was harvested illegally. Vegetation and soil were impacted, the spill was within the company's right of way, a section of the bulkline was harvested illegally by an unknown vandals. (4) The Oil spill was also

identified along 24 inches Trans Escravos Pipeline at Obotobo. The cause of this spill was that an illegal 4 inches valve was attached on the company's pipeline. (5) Another spill was noticed along 24" Trans Forcados Pipeline at Obotobo 2, this was due to the connection of 4inches hot tap valve installed at 12 O' clock position of the company's pipeline. (6) At Yeye Community there was a spill along 28 inches Trans-Forcados Pipeline. Despite that the spill occur within the company right of way, Vegetation and Soil were impacted. (7) The spray of oil spill was still discovered along Forcados Terminal Skimming Pit and along Nigerian Company B (Naoc) in Beneboye Cluster Flowline at Okutu Ogulagha Row. Vegetation and surface water were

impacted, the spill was within and outside the company's right of way, and there was a backout flow of crude oil as a failure at the check valve in the skimming pit. (8) Along 24 inches Trans Ramos Pipeline at Odimodi the spill also occurred, It was observed that a cofferdam was constructed around the 24 inches Trans Ramos Pipeline. But, the pipeline was not leaking. (9) Oil spill was discovered along 28 inches of Trans Forcados Pipeline at Odidi and around Orugbene a Location at Kenlogbene. It was observed that Vegetation, surface water and soil were impacted, dead floating fishes was sighted, the spill was within and outside the company's right of way. Table 5.1 is the summary of Oil spill location in the study area.

Figure 5.1: Map showing the spatial Distribution of Oil spill Location In the study area (Source: Researcher’s GIS lab, 2022)

Spatial Location of Oil spill within the study area

Code	Latitude	Longitude	location	Description of the Location
S1	5.456639	5.234306	Company A. (SPDC) 4" Yokri Well 114s Flowline At Yokri.	Vegetation, Surface Water and Topsoil were impacted. The spill was within the company's right of way.
S2	5.428611	5.273889	6" Yokri Cluster 51 Bulkline B2 - Manifold 4	Vegetation and soil were impacted, the spill was within the company's right of way.
S3	5.418257	5.30253	SPDC 6" Yokri Manifold 1 Cluster 95 Bulkline @ Obotobo	A section of Bulkline was harvested Illegally. Vegetation and soil were impacted, the spill was within the company's right of way, a section of the bulkline was harvested illegally by an unknown vandals.
S4	5.403053	5.339439	24" Trans Escravos Pipeline At Obotobo	An illegal 4" valve was attached on the company's pipeline.
S5	5.394781	5.363222	24" Trans Forcados Pipeline @ Obotobo 2	4" hot tap valve installed at 12 O' clock position of the company's pipeline.
S6	5.421456	5.379997	28" Trans-Forcados Pipeline At Yeye Community.	Vegetation and Soil were impacted. The spill was within the company's right of way.
S7	5.3375	5.350444	Forcados Terminal Skimming Pit	Vegetation and surface water were impacted, the spill was within and outside the company's right of way, There was a backout flow of crude oil as a failure at the check valve in the skimming pit
S8	5.313805	5.335268	Naoc Beneboye Cluster Flowline At Okutu Ogulagha Row	

S9	5.235944	5.383581	24" Trans Ramos Pipeline At Odimodi.	It was observed by the JIT that a cofferdam was constructed around the 24" Trans Ramos Pipeline. But, the pipeline was not leaking.
S10	5.359167	5.485278	28" Trans Forcados Pipeline @ Odidi.	Vegetation, surface water and soil were impacted, dead floating fishes was sighted, the spill was within and outside the company's right of way.
S11	5.300389	5.556667	Orugbene A Location At Kenlogbene	

Source: Author's Laboratory 2022

ANALYSIS OF THE ABIOTIC ECOLOGICAL FACTORS

Assessment of Temporal Impact of Oil Spill on Vegetation and wet land Greenness.

Oil spills affect different elements of abiotic ecology at different levels (De la Huz, Lastra, and López, 2018), with vegetation and wetlands being the most impacted because of their location at the intertidal zone of the marine ecosystem (Jana, Maiti and Biswas, 2015). The vegetation indices of 2010,2015 and 2020 were use to assess the impact of oil spill on vegetation and wetland . As depicted in **Figure 5.2.1.1**,:

- the NDVI the graph of the vegetation and wetland in the study area showed a general decrease in vegetation health from 2010 to 2015.

- From 2010 to 2020 the vegetation and wetland in Block E and F were extremely affected by the spill because the NDVI detected are between the low range value of greenness (- 0.4987 to 0.1)
- In 2010 most of the vegetation in other oil block were in good health condition and the NDVI value are high and were between (0.3926 - 0.47017),
- In 2015 the Block B and C were highly affected and the NDVI is Low in the range of (0.10 - 0.2089)
- From 2015 to 2020 only the vegetation in the block D, M ,L were in very good health. The other block were slightly affected by oil spill and the NDVI is range of 0.2089 - 0.3926, Evaluation of NDVI From 2010 to 2020

Oil Block Code	NDVI (2010)	NDVI (2015)	NDVI (2020)	Threshold
A	0.4760	0.2225	0.3256	0.2000
B	0.4103	0.1548	0.2473	0.2000
C	0.4590	0.1713	0.2548	0.2000
D	0.6210	0.4370	0.5330	0.2000

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E	-0.1828	-0.2913	-0.4639	0.2000
F	0.0788	-0.0050	-0.1572	0.2000
G	0.4950	0.3490	0.3458	0.2000
J	0.4985	0.3547	0.3754	0.2000
K	0.5619	0.3384	0.4503	0.2000
L	0.6100	0.4210	0.4326	0.2000
M	0.6072	0.4908	0.4162	0.2000
Average	0.4214	0.2403	0.2509	0.2000

Figure 5.2.1.1: Graph shown the Trend of affected Vegetation and Wetland (2010-2020) . Source: Researchers’ Field work 2022

2010

a) 2015

Figure 5.2.1.2: Map showing the spatial changes of affected Vegetation and Wetland (2010-2020)

Source: Researchers’ Field work 2022

Assessment of Temporal Impact of Oil Spill on the Dryness of soil and built up.

Soil hydrophobicity is known to adversely affect hydrological and ecological soil functions by decreasing infiltration, increasing surface runoff and erosion, and impeding plant growth and germination (Li et al., 1997, Dekker et al., 2005). The table 5.2.2 is the evaluation of Intelligent Building Index value over the period of 2010 till 2020. The Graph Fig 5.2.2.1 shown that generally

they are very low IBI value from 2010 to 2020, this shows that the Soil hydrophobicity is low.

- In 2010 only the block E and F was affected by high dryness Phenomenon, this could affect the soil infiltration in those block.
- In 2015 it revealed that none of the block were affected by the dryness Phenomenon on soil infiltration.
- In 2020 the block D,M , L and F were only affected by a medium dryness phenomenon on soil infiltration.

Table 5.2.2: Evaluation of Intelligent Building Index (IBI) for soil dryness

Oil Block Code	IBI (2010)	IBI (2015)	IBI (2020)
A	-0.1967	-0.9941	-0.0231
B	-0.1998	-0.9960	-0.0200
C	-0.2249	-0.9978	-0.0169
D	-0.1883	-0.9829	0.0206
E	0.1477	-0.7090	-0.2087
F	0.3216	-0.2505	0.0521
G	-0.2153	-0.9991	-0.0037
J	-0.2365	-1.0000	-0.0174
K	-0.2591	-1.0000	-0.0264
L	-0.2149	-0.9971	0.0128
M	-0.1785	-0.9839	0.0304
Average	-0.1313	-0.9009	-0.0182

Figure 5.2.2.1: Graph shown the Trend of Soil Dryness (2010-2020)

Source: Researchers' Field work 2022

Figure 5.2.2.2: Map shown the spatial changes of Soil Dryness (2010-2020)

Source: Researchers’ Field work 2022

Assessment of Temporal Impact of Oil Spill on the humidity of soil and vegetation:

Oil spills can impact both the physical and chemical properties of soil. Soil moisture is one of the most variable aspects, changing frequently due to factors such as precipitation, evapotranspiration, infiltration, and runoff, often fluctuating daily and seasonally. The

moisture content in any soil landscape can differ over time and space, influenced by environmental conditions, plant interactions, soil characteristics, cycles of wetting and drying, and various other factors. The graph 5.2.3.1 shows that the humidity of soil and vegetation has decreased in all the block over time from 2010 to 2020. Figure 5.2.3.2 shows a high concentration of wetness in block E in 2010. This may be due to some climate factor.

Table 5.2.3: Evaluation of the humidity of soil and vegetation

Oil Block Code	Wet2010	Wet2015	Wet2020	threshold
A	-0.0725	-0.0763	-0.1296	0.0000
B	-0.0572	-0.0620	-0.1123	0.0000
C	-0.0509	-0.0602	-0.1051	0.0000
D	-0.1027	-0.1502	-0.1981	0.0000
E	-0.0082	0.0165	-0.0044	0.0000
F	-0.0387	-0.0449	-0.0730	0.0000
G	-0.0703	-0.0932	-0.1541	0.0000
J	-0.0575	-0.0921	-0.1507	0.0000
K	-0.0539	-0.0853	-0.1299	0.0000
L	-0.0818	-0.1173	-0.1904	0.0000
M	-0.1016	-0.1459	-0.2011	0.0000
Average	-0.0632	-0.0828	-0.1317	

Source: Researchers’ Field work 2022

Figure 5.2.3.1: Graph shown the Trend of the humidity of soil and vegetation (2010-2020)
Source: Researchers’ Field work 2022

Figure 5.2.3.2: Map showing the spatial changes of the humidity of soil and vegetation (2010-2020) :

Source: Researchers’ Field work 2022

Assessment of Temporal Impact of Oil Spill on the Temperature of the area.

Temperatures have an important role to salinity and the stability of emulsion on oil. The table 5.2.4 is the evaluation of the Land Surface Temperature (LST) of the oil spill environment. The average LST shows that that the temperature of the area are in normal condition throughout the period of 2010 to 2020. The graph (figure

5.2.4.1) has shown that only the oil block E have a variety of very high temperature in 2010 it was 34.4560 °C it has increased to 45.3454 °C and 56.2980 °C in 2015 and 2020. The threshold of normal temperature in 28 °C. The spatial change of the normal LST of block D in 2010 is about 27.6719 °C which increased to high degree in 2015 about 28.3050 °C. In 2020 The High temperature shifted from D to nearby Block (M) at 28.0468 °C.

Evaluation of the Environmental Temperature

Oil Block Code	LST 2010 (°C)	LST 2015 (°C)	LST 2020 (°C)	Threshold (°C)
A	24.8286	26.8437	26.6764	28
B	25.3804	26.9973	26.0917	
C	25.0953	26.7235	26.1211	
D	27.6719	28.3050	27.7775	
E	34.4560	45.3454	56.2980	
F	24.4742	26.5722	26.2510	
G	24.4412	26.7896	27.1167	
J	24.3976	26.8010	27.4585	
K	24.7593	26.9417	25.7107	
L	24.5890	27.0681	27.8153	
M	25.9279	27.7524	28.0468	
Average	26.0019	28.7400	29.5785	

Source: Researchers’ Field work 2022

Figure 5.2.4.1: Graph shown the Trend of the Environmental Temperature (2010-2020)

Source: Researchers’ Field work 2022

Figure 5.2.3.2: Map showing the spatial changes of the environmental temperature (2010-2020)

Source: Researchers' Field work 2022

Conclusion

The Ecological Index (EI) has emerged as a valuable tool in ecological environment monitoring, offering advantages of rapidity, real-time assessment, and wide-ranging coverage. Its effectiveness in evaluating regional ecological environments has been widely acknowledged. However, a recent study on ecological risk assessment of oil spill impacts on the Forcado River in the Delta region has demonstrated the potential of EI in assessing ecological health. Specifically, indices such as NDVI (greenness of forest ecosystems), IBI (soil dryness), heat index (Land Surface Temperature), and humidity index. A Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of NDVI, WET, LST, and IBI data from 2010 to 2020 revealed significant impacts of oil spills on vegetation (vegetation wetness) have been employed. . This study highlights the limitations of relying on a single ecological factor to objectively and comprehensively reflect changes in ecological environments. Instead, it emphasizes the importance of evaluating regional ecological environments through the combined effects of multiple ecological factors, as exemplified by the Remote Sensing Ecological Index (RSEI) proposed by Hanqiu Xu (2013). The RSEI integrates remote sensing information and natural factors, enabling rapid and simple assessments of regional ecological quality based on the contribution of each index to the first principal component. This study conducted a comprehensive analysis of oil spills in the study area between 2010 and 2020.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations are proposed to mitigate the

environmental and socio-economic impacts of oil spills in the Forcados River region. First, **there is an urgent need for improved oil spill monitoring and response systems** through the deployment of **satellite remote sensing, drones, and real-time sensors** along pipeline corridors to detect leaks early and prevent large-scale contamination. Oil companies operating in the region must also **enhance their maintenance protocols, replace aging infrastructure, and adopt more durable pipeline materials** to reduce spill occurrences caused by corrosion and equipment failure. Additionally, **the government should strengthen regulatory enforcement by imposing stricter penalties on oil companies that fail to report and remediate spills promptly.** There should also be **greater transparency in environmental audits, ensuring that both corporate and artisanal spills are accurately documented and addressed.**

To address the ecological damage, **comprehensive remediation and land restoration programs should be implemented** in highly polluted areas. This includes the **use of bioremediation techniques, such as hydrocarbon-degrading microorganisms and phytoremediation with resilient plant species,** to restore soil and wetland health. The government should establish **protected conservation zones around critical mangrove forests** to prevent further degradation and support biodiversity recovery. Additionally, **regular environmental impact assessments (EIAs)** should be mandated

before new oil exploration or extraction activities commence to minimize potential hazards.

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